

The Effect of Decision-Making Styles on Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies

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Abstract

The use of environments in real estate marketing is seeing a steady growth on a daily basis. To effectively address the growing expectations in the field of digital media design, designers must accurately identify and assess the demands and requirements, while conducting a comprehensive analysis of the elements that influence these expectations. The main objective of this study was to ascertain the anticipated requirements and desires of real estate clientele in relation to digital technology. One of the key responsibilities of marketing include

influencing the decision-making processes of clients and providing support in their purchase choices. Given the high cost, variability, extensive use of resources, and potential for investment, consumers are faced with the need to carefully assess several factors when making a choice to acquire real estate goods. The effective handling of gathered information presents challenges in the decision-making process. The key concern in the realm of digital media designs is in effectively and lucidly delivering pertinent product information to buyers. The primary objective of information collection is to enhance the process of decision making. Various decision-making styles are used by customers throughout the decision-making process. This research aimed to examine the potential impact of decision-making styles on consumers' expectations about digital technology.

Keywords: The Effect of Decision-Making, Styles on Real Estate, Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies, The Effect of Decision-Making, Styles on Real Estate

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Introduction

The expectations of reality estate customers from the technological environments that are used extensively in real estate marketing are increasing day by day. In order for digital media designers to meet the increasing expectations, they need to determine the demands and needs correctly and analyze the factors affecting the expectations in detail. The primary purpose of this research was to determine the expectations of reality estate customers from digital technologies. One of the tasks of marketing is to shape the decision-making structures of customers and to assist the purchasing decision – due to the fact that real estate products are expensive, not similar to each other's, too many materials are used in their production, and can be considered as an investment tool, customers have to evaluate a lot of information when making a purchase decision – Accurate processing of the collected information complicates the decision-making process. The most important issue in digital media designs is to clearly present the information that customers need about the products. The purpose of collecting information is to facilitate decision making. Customers use different types of decision-making styles when making decisions. In this study, it was investigated whether decision-making styles have a direct effect on customers' expectations from digital technologies.

In The Decision-Making Process

In the decision-making process with digital marketing, customers can access more information and learn about the features of the alternatives of the product they are interested in. Customers can compare the features of the products and see the comments and experiences of the people who have bought the product before. Purchasing decisions are made as a result of research conducted in mobile and information technologies.

Property selection and spatial decision making involves a complex process of choosing the best alternative from a range of viable alternatives (Emekli & Caner, 2019). Today, digital applications are being developed in order to clearly reveal the needs and requirements of real estate customers. With such applications, the list of features that customers want to see is determined, then the market value of real estates suitable for these features is determined, and suggestions are made to customers for purchasing, selling and renting decisions. The application serves as a decision support system for real estate customers (Lopez, del Monte, & Montero, Fuzzy Logic in Real Estate Valuation, 2008).

Expectations of real estate customers from digital technologies

Real estate properties are often tangible goods that are visually seen by potential buyers who express a desire to purchase them. In recent times, virtual environments have been developed to cater to the demands of clients over the internet. These settings aim to provide simulated tours of actual residences. Several research have been conducted to examine the emotional responses of consumers when they visit actual surroundings in virtual settings. These studies have yielded findings that closely align with the emotional experiences reported by individuals in real-world scenarios. The research conducted aim to examine whether virtual journeys may effectively stimulate clients' purchasing intentions. It has been determined that the inclination to make a purchase is stimulated in a favorable manner.

In contemporary times, just seeing and observing a real estate property is insufficient for clients in the process of making a purchase. Further and comprehensive data is required, including the socioeconomic standing of the residents residing in the surrounding area, the caliber of education offered by the neighboring educational institutions, and the speed of internet connectivity as a component of the infrastructure.

In contemporary online market situations where real estate ads are conducted, the information provided to clients is deemed inadequate in light of the growing demands. Customers have a need to acquire a greater amount of information pertaining to financial assistance, investment profitability, energy efficiency, and also want access to consultation services as and when required. The recognition of the potential of robots to enhance human existence has been attributed to the advancements in artificial intelligence technologies. In contemporary society, clients possess a prevailing anticipation for seamless access to information and instantaneous communication facilitated by a wide array of technical gadgets. Moreover, digital environments that are integrated with artificial intelligence provide help for the process of making purchase decisions.

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Effective decision-making styles in real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies

The use of digital technology by real estate clients is driven by the anticipation that such tools would facilitate their decision-making endeavors. The concept of "decision making" is often seen as the manifestation of choice behavior (Connor & Becker, 2003). Efficient execution of the real estate marketing process by intermediary businesses and manufacturers requires accurate analysis of the aspects that influence consumers' decision-making behavior.

Behavioral problems often arise as a result of the expectations that real estate customers have about their requirements being fulfilled. Occasionally, consumers are able to articulate their needs in a clear manner, but in other instances, certain variables may remain ambiguous or beyond the customers' awareness or understanding. However, through the diligent efforts of marketers, these undisclosed requirements might be uncovered. The aforementioned criteria are referred to as fuzzy factors in the study conducted by Lopez, Santos, and Montero (2010) on fuzzy specification in real estate market decision-making. The components that are explicitly articulated are associated with the cognitive aspect of attitude, while the ambiguous factors often pertain to the emotional dimension of attitude. When consumers are faced with a purchase decision, they often have the option to use either a logical decision-making style, which is based on analysis, or an intuitive decision-making style, which is based on emotions. This choice is made after gathering relevant information about the goods. The individual often employs a hybrid decision-making approach, including elements of both intellectual and emotional considerations. Prior to reaching a choice, consumers often rely on the perspectives of others, draw from their prior experiences to make prompt judgments, or choose to refrain from making a decision (Scott & Bruce, 1995). The emotional decision-making style in real estate marketing garners attention from both production businesses and marketers. Research done in Japan using the Kansei engineering technique yielded the finding that a linear correlation exists between the emotional states of real estate clients and their purchase choices (Llinares & Page, 2011).

Rational decision making

In the context of the rational decision-making process, a greater degree of attention and effort is typically allocated. This is often accompanied by a heightened level of uncertainty within the surrounding environment, leading to an increase in doubts regarding potential solutions. In order to ensure consistency with prior choices and decisions, individuals engage

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in self-criticism. Ultimately, the appropriate course of action is determined by carefully comparing and evaluating all relevant details pertaining to the problem at hand. The subject under investigation is currently being examined.

At the conclusion of the cognitive process, it is anticipated that consumers would engage in decision-making that is based on rationality. In the field of economics, individuals that exhibit rational decision-making behavior are often referred to as Homo Economicus. The preferences that please sensible beings are in alignment with their wants. According to Urbina and Villaverde (2019), these persons may be characterized as individuals who have made a choice that maximizes their own benefits and, in turn, benefits society as a whole. Rationality may be regarded as the foundational element in the realm of consumer choice process study. Nevertheless, some study findings have shown that consumers deviate from rationality in their decision-making processes' latter stages. The disparity in evaluations may be attributed to variations in individuals' assessment capabilities, as shown by factors such as crises, economic instability, restricted alternatives, distinction of mental capacities, limited information, and diverse emotional dispositions among people (Kamber, 2018). Due to this rationale, there exists a proclivity to embrace the notion of bounded rationality, first introduced by Herbert A. Simon, as opposed to absolute rationality.

A rational consumer may be characterized as an individual who employs logical reasoning and utilizes the knowledge and computational resources at their disposal to make sound judgments. The use of restricted information in decision-making processes, particularly in contexts characterized by uncertainty, might provide challenges in accurately understanding the external environment. The presence of non-rational processes, motivation, emotions, and sensory cues throughout the process of reasoning leads individuals to try to understand a given situation by directing their attention. Consequently, the notion of limited rationality seems to be a more realistic and logical framework, as opposed to the idea of pure rationality. According to Simon (1986), one may argue that it is an approach. The human body has cognitive and emotional capacities that enable it to effectively address challenges arising from its environment. Habits serve to optimize and streamline human behaviors. Habits are acquired via the process of learning. The process of acquiring knowledge and insights via the examination of prior erroneous choices facilitates the ability to make more accurate and effortless selections

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in subsequent endeavors. The significance of habit stability is seen crucial not just at the individual level but also within the context of society. The use of practical thinking offers a convenient means through which several challenges may be effectively surmounted. The aforementioned scenario highlights the need of using intuitive decision-making strategies when confronted with novel challenges (Twomey, 1998).

Intuitive decision making

Intuitive decision making encompasses the utilization of familiarity, recognition, similarity, awareness, simple relationships, and simple causal connections. This approach facilitates the resolution of recurring problems and the exploration of straightforward solutions to complex problems, particularly in situations characterized by limited information availability. During situations that need prompt decision-making and impose time constraints, individuals prefer to rely more on intuitive decision-making due to its expeditious nature, whereas logical decision-making tends to be slower in comparison.

The efficacy of intuition is diminished under states of emotional disturbance and unhappiness. When an individual experiences positive affect, they may demonstrate enhanced creativity via the use of intuitive decision-making processes. However, it is important to note that the display of imprudent actions might lead to the occurrence of logical errors. In his seminal work, Kahneman (2003) coined the terms "system 1" and "system 2" to refer to the intuitive and logical decision-making processes, respectively. The second system is tasked with verifying the suggestions generated by the first system. Human beings have a natural inclination towards intuitive decision-making, referred to as the first system. However, when faced with unfamiliar or knowledge-deficient situations, individuals are compelled to engage the second system, which involves a rational decision-making process. The individual noted that System 2 has a tendency to endorse the choices made by System 1 due to its inclination towards cognitive lethargy.

Dependent decision making

The dependent decision-making style refers to a decision-making approach whereby an individual relies on the assistance and guidance of others, rather than making independent

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decisions. This decision-making approach involves actively seeking the views and guidance of others. In instances of this kind, individuals may have feelings of inadequacy when faced with decision-making, prompting them to seek external validation and approval for their choices. According to Bodin, Chermack, and Coons (2016), Customers often adopt a dependent decision-making style when faced with high-priced products or products that include complicated features. In contemporary times, the extensive array of choices and functionalities associated with available items poses a challenge in terms of doing thorough research and arriving at informed selections. The inclusion of customer reviews facilitates the decision-making process for prospective buyers by providing insights from those who have previously purchased and used the product. Numerous platforms within the digital marketing landscape aim to assist clients in this aspect. In recent times, there has been a notable increase in the preference for digital marketing platforms among consumers, mostly attributed to the availability of software for convenient comparison of product costs and features.

Quick decision making

The concept of quick decision-making pertains to the process of making immediate choices. The decision-making style in question is often used under circumstances characterized by a pressing need for prompt decision-making. According to the study conducted by Bovolar and Orosova (2015), The use of this approach is common in the process of making purchase selections for items that possess a low price point and a limited number of features. Nevertheless, the use of this decision-making technique becomes challenging when acquiring high-priced things with several characteristics, such as real estate. The quick decision-making style is characterized by a propensity for making decisions rapidly, which is associated with a higher level of risk-taking. In situations when prompt decision-making is required, it is possible that crucial information necessary for making an informed choice may be absent. The accuracy of the assessment may be compromised as a result of insufficient information. Real estate goods are assets that have the potential to maintain or appreciate in value over an extended period of time, hence safeguarding the initial investment made in them. The purchases in question are seen to possess relatively low levels of risk compared to other investment vehicles. In fact, they may be regarded as acquisitions made with the intention of mitigating risk in conjunction with other investment instruments. During times characterized by rising prices, clients who engage in early purchasing might get advantages from their purchases in comparison to those who make

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later purchases. However, the duration for the return of the invested price to the consumer may vary significantly based on the specific kind of real estate acquired and the potential misplacement of the acquisition. While it is advisable to use caution when making real estate purchases, it is equally important to avoid delaying the buying decision by closely monitoring key economic indicators.

Avoid making decisions

This decision-making method is often used in situations characterized by a high degree of ambiguity, intricate product details, and an indeterminate assessment of the benefits associated with the intended purchase. Individuals who choose for this particular approach to decision-making often exhibit a tendency to defer and postpone the choice, deferring the process of contemplation and implementation of a solution to a later point in time. According to Burhanoglu (2016), Individuals that engage in this particular mode of decision-making have a tendency to defer decision-making until a state of heightened pressure is reached, maybe due to experiencing discomfort or unease when confronted with the subject matter under consideration (Rotbring, 2010).

RESEARCH METHOD

Universe and Sample

The scope of this study encompasses the whole population of individuals who engage in real estate transactions. The sample comprises 433 individuals with varying characteristics such as age, gender, income level, education level, number of households, and jobs. These individuals may be accessed via social media platforms and have shown interest in participating in the survey.

Data Collection Method and Tool

The study used a questionnaire as the technique for data gathering. The survey was administered using the Google Documents survey program, and it was disseminated to the participants using internet communication apps, allowing them to provide their responses through both PCs and mobile devices.

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Scales Used in the Study

Two distinct scales were used throughout the formulation of the study questions. The "General Decision-Making Styles Scale," developed by Scott and Bruce in 1995, was used to ascertain decision-making styles. The inquiries pertaining to the Dependent variable, namely Real Estate Customers' Expectation for Digital Technologies, were established by an extensive examination of relevant scholarly literature and an investigation into the current and emerging digital applications in the field.

Statistical Analysis Methods

The data analysis was conducted using the SPSS package software and the AMOS program. The scales produced for each variable were subjected to reliability analyses and exploratory factor analyses (EFA) using the SPSS software package. The AMOS software was used to do confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), route analysis, and structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis.

Findings and Interpretation

Table 1 Demographic Information

Demographic Information		f_i	%
Age	18-30	270	62.4
	31-45	98	22.6
	46-55	48	11.1
	56-65	9	2.1
	66 years and older	8	1.8
	Total	433	100.0
Gender	Woman	203	46.9
	Male	230	53.1
	Total	433	100.0
Income Level	1-5000	258	59.6
	6000 - 10 000	121	27.9
	11 000 – 15 000	33	7.6
	16 000 – 20 000	13	3.0
	21 000 and above	8	1.8
	Total	433	100.0
Job	Officer	84	19.4
	Private Sector employee	55	12.7

	Self-employment	23	5.3
	Farmer	7	1.6
	Employee	26	6.0
	Retired	14	3.2
	Student	187	43.2
	Housewife	20	4.6
	Not working	17	3.9
	Total	433	100.0
Education level	Primary education	15	3,5
	secondary education	56	12.9
	Associate Degree	132	30.5
	Licence	200	46.2
	graduate	30	6.9
	Total	433	100.0
Number of Households	one	28	6.5
	2	56	12.9
	3	102	23.6
	4	124	28.6
	5 and above	123	28.4
	Total	433	100.0

Upon examination of Table 1, it is seen that 62.4% (n=270) of the participants fall into the age range of "18-30". Additionally, 22.6% (n=98) of the participants are categorized within the age range of "31-45". Furthermore, it is noted that 11.1% of the participants also belong to the "31-45" age range. Out of a total sample size of 48 individuals, 2.1% (n=9) were under the age range of 46-55, while 2.1% (n=9) were in the age range of 56-65. Additionally, 1.8% (n=8) of the participants were discovered to be aged 66 and above. Upon analyzing the participants with respect to the gender variable, it was observed that 53.1% (n=230) of the participants identified as "male," while 46.9% (n=203) identified as "female." When analyzing the participants in the study with respect to the variable of income level, it was found that 59.6% (n=256) fell within the range of "1-5,000TL". Additionally, 27.9% (n=121) reported an income between "6,000-10,000TL". A smaller proportion, 7% (n=33), indicated their income to be between "11,000 – 15,000 TL". Furthermore, 3% (n=13) stated their income to be within the range of "16,000 – 20,000 TL". Lastly, a minority of 1.8% (n=8) reported an income of "21,000 TL and above". It is evident that the individual has a source of financial earnings. Upon analyzing the participants based on their occupation, it was found that 43.2% (n=187) identified as "students," 19.4% (n=84) as "civil servants," and 12.7% (n=55) as "private" individuals. In the survey, 26 individuals (6%) identified themselves as "sector employees," 23 individuals

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(5.3%) identified themselves as "workers," and 20 individuals (4.6%) identified themselves as "self-employed." Additionally, a percentage of respondents (not specified) identified themselves as "housewives." The data reveals that a proportion of 3.9% (n=17) may be categorized as "not working," while 3.2% (n=14) fall under the classification of "retired." Additionally, a smaller percentage of 1.6% (n=7) can be identified as "farmers." When examining the participants based on the variable of education level, it was found that 46.2% (n=200) identified as "undergraduate", 30.5% (n=132) identified as "associate degree", and 12.9% (n=56) identified as... The data reveals that 6.9% (n=30) of the participants possess a "secondary education" level, while another 6.9% (n=30) have achieved a "graduate" level of education. Additionally, 3.5% (n=15) of the participants have attained a "primary education" level. When examining the participants with respect to the variable of household number, it was found that 28.6% (n=124) belonged to the category labeled "4", while 28.4% (n=123) fell into the category labeled "5 and above". Additionally, 23.6% (n=102) of the participants were classified under the category labeled "3". The data reveals that the category labeled as "3" accounted for 12.9% (n=56) of the total sample, whereas the category labeled as "2" accounted for 6.5% (n=28), respectively.

Research Model

This research aimed to examine the potential impact of decision-making styles on the expectations of real estate clients regarding digital technology.

Figure 1. Research model III (Respectively; Rational decision making, Intuitive decision making, Dependent decision making, Quick decision making, avoiding decision making, --- Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies)

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Research model validity analyzes

The scales' construct validity was assessed using EFA and CFA techniques. Initially, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed in order to investigate the disentanglement of the components underlying the items within the scale. The KMO value of the scale is 0.88 as a consequence of the implementation of the EFA. The Bartlett test statistic for the scale was determined to be 6908.453, with a p-value of less than 0.001. The findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) revealed that the scale had six distinct sub-factors, which are shown in Table 22. The sub-factors account for 74% of the overall variation seen in the scale. When considering the explained variance ratio, the dimensions are arranged in descending order based on their respective explanation ratios. The dimension labeled "BEK" has the highest explanation ratio of 26.18%, making it the first dimension. Following this, the second dimension is denoted as "RKV" with an explanation ratio of 11.98%. Lastly, the third dimension is referred to as the third dimension, without specifying its explanation ratio. The fourth dimension is denoted as "SKV" and has a disclosure rate of 10.03%. Similarly, the fourth dimension is represented by "BKV" and has a disclosure rate of 8.91%. The fifth dimension is labeled as "KVK" and has a disclosure rate of 8.73%. Lastly, the dimension with the lowest disclosure rate is referred to as "HKV" and has a rate of 8.56%.

A total of 23 items, including almost half of the original scale (48 items), were excluded from further analysis due to their factor loadings falling below the threshold of 0.75 and their observed associations with other factors. The scale is composed of six dimensions, each with a varying number of items. The first dimension, labeled "NEC," includes nine items. The second dimension, labeled "RCV," consists of four items. The third dimension, labeled "SKV," comprises three items. The fourth dimension, labeled "BKV," contains three items. The fifth dimension, labeled "KVK," consists of three items. Lastly, the sixth dimension, labeled "HKV," also includes three items. The phenomenon under consideration has been observed. Table 19 presents the findings of the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) for the scale.

Table 2. EFA results for the research model scale

Sub-Dimensions	1. Factor	2. Factor	3. Factor	4. Factor	5. Factor	6. Factor
BEK7	0.852					
BEK8	0.837					

BEK9	0.863					
BEK10	0.858					
BEK11	0.871					
BEK12	0.847					
BEK13	0.820					
BEK17	0.826					
BEK19	0.798					
RKV2		0.770				
RKV3		0.800				
RKV4		0.867				
RKV5		0.829				
SKV1			0.832			
SKV2			0.850			
SKV5			0.812			
BKV3				0.833		
BKV4				0.839		
BKV5				0.805		
KVK2					0.861	
KVK3					0.881	
KVK5					0.849	
HKV1						0.814
HKV2						0.824
HKV3						0.822
Total	6,546	2,996	2,507	2,228	2,183	2,140
Explained Variance (%)	26,184	11,984	10,030	8,911	8,733	8,559
Cumulative Explained Variance (%)	26,184	38,168	48,198	57,109	65,842	74,401
KMO Test Value			0.882			
Bartlett Sphericity Test Value			6908,453			
Bartlett test p Value			0.0001			

Table 3. Model Factor Distribution

Factor 1: BEK	
BEK 7:	I would like the real estate company website or mobile application to provide information about the energy efficiency of buildings listed for sale and rent.

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BEK 8:	I would like to have a system on the real estate company website or mobile application that compares the price increase trends in the region I am interested in for the last ten years and shows the forecasts for the future.
BEK 9:	I would like to have a system installed on the real estate company website or mobile application, which calculates the income I will gain by comparing the existing investment tools with real estate investment.
BEK 10:	On the real estate company website or mobile application, I would like to show the customer references and the opinions of the customers who have shopped about the construction company and the real estate company before.
BEK 11:	I would like to have a system installed on the real estate company website or mobile application, which compares the properties in the region I am interested in and shows the lowest, highest and average prices.
BEK 12:	I would like real estate and construction companies to have QR codes on their signs, advertisements and business cards, so that I can access their for sale and rental lists.
BEK 13:	I would like their help and advice on decision making through recommendation systems on the real estate company website or mobile application.
BEK 17:	I would like the real estate company website or mobile application to provide information about the renovations that the properties for sale and rental will need and the estimated costs.
BEK 19:	I would like the real estate company mobile app to show the properties for rent and sale in the area closest to me.
Factor 2: RKV	
RKV 2:	I try to have the right facts before making a decision.
RKV 3:	I make decisions logically and systematically.
RKV 4:	I need to think carefully before making a decision.
RKV 5:	I consider various options when making a decision on an issue.

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3. Factor: SKV	
SC 1:	I trust my instincts when making decisions.
SC 2:	I usually tend to trust my intuition when making decisions.
SKV 5:	When making a decision, I rely on my reactions based on my inner feelings.
Factor 4: BKV	
BKV 3:	It is easier for me to make important decisions when I have the support of others.
BKV 4:	I use the advice of others when making important decisions.
BKV 5:	I like having someone to point me in the right direction when I'm faced with important decisions.
5. Factor: KVK	
KVK 2:	I postpone making decisions as long as possible.
KVK 3:	I often postpone important decisions.
KVK 5:	I put off many decisions because thinking about them makes me uncomfortable.
Factor 6: HKV	
HKV 1:	I usually make sudden decisions.
HKV 2:	I often make split-second decisions.
HKV 3:	I make quick decisions.

Table 19 presents the findings of the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) conducted using the data received from the research group. The findings of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) reveal that the scale has six sub-factors. The "IEC" sub-factor of the scale has nine items, with factor load values ranging from 0.798 to 0.871. This sub-factor accounts for 26.18% of the overall variance. The second component is denoted as "RKV" and is comprised of a total of four elements. The factor load values exhibit a range from 0.770 to 0.867, and together account for 11.98% of the overall variation. The third element is denoted as "SKV" and is comprised of three distinct things. The factor load values exhibit a range of 0.812 to 0.850, collectively accounting for 10.03% of the total explained variation. The fourth element, denoted as "BKV,"

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has a total of three items. The factor loadings for the items inside this factor range from 0.805 to 0.839, and together account for 8.91% of the total variance. The fifth component in the study is referred to as "KVK," and it comprises a sub-factor that encompasses three distinct elements. The factor loading values of the items associated with this factor range from 0.849 to 0.881, and together account for 8.73% of the total variance. The sixth element, denoted as "HKV," comprises a set of three distinct items. The factor load values of the items pertaining to this dimension exhibit a range of 0.814 to 0.824, and together account for 8.56% of the total variance. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that six variables account for about 74% of the overall variation.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used to examine the scale, resulting in the identification of sub-factors. A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted in order to assess the precision of the components identified via exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and to see whether they constituted a valid measurement model. The DFA analysis was conducted using the AMOS 24 software suite. Prior to conducting parameter estimates in Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), an assessment was performed to ascertain the suitability of the data for a multivariate normal distribution. This evaluation was conducted to establish the most acceptable approach for parameter estimation. The findings of the multivariate normal distribution are shown in Table 21. The multivariate normal distribution test yielded a p-value of 0.0001 and a z-value of 77,379. Based on the acquired values, it was deduced that the data did not exhibit multivariate normal distribution. In this particular instance, the analysis was conducted using the maximum likelihood approach (Maximum Likelihood).

Table 4. CRÖ multivariate normality values

	kurtosis	Z value
AMOS	273,261	77,379

The researchers used a main level Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to assess the validity and reliability of the scale utilized in examining the impact of decision-making styles on the expectations of real estate clients about digital technology. The analysis findings and

route diagram for the main level Discriminant Function Analysis (DFA) are shown in Figure 8 and Table 22, respectively.

Figure 2. Model III Primary level DFA and Standardized Values

RKV: Rational Decision Making; SKV: Intuitive Decision Making; BKV: Dependent Decision Making; KVK: Avoiding Decision Making; HKV: Quick Decision Making; BEK: Real Estate Customers' Expectations from Digital Technologies

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Initially, an analysis was conducted on the fitness index values for Model III. The Normed Fit Index (NFI) is a statistical measure derived from index values. The Comparative Fit metric (CFI) is a normalized fit metric used in structural equation modeling (SEM). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) are both measures used in statistical analysis to assess the fit of a model. The Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is a statistical measure used to assess the goodness of fit of a statistical model. The GFI value was adjusted to account for the sample size. The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is a statistical measure used in academic research to assess the goodness-of-fit of a structural equation model. The square root of standardized mean errors, often known as the root mean square error approximation (RMSEA), is a statistical measure. The value of the mean square root of estimated errors, denoted as χ^2 / sd , is calculated by dividing the chi-square by the degrees of freedom.

Table 5. Primary level DFA fit indices and results for the model

Index	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	Results
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI \leq 0.95$	0.92
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0.95
GFI	$0.90 \leq GFI \leq 0.95$	$0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	0.90
AGFI	$0.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$0.85 \leq AGFI \leq 0.90$	0.88
SRMR	$0.00 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.05
RMSEA	$0.00 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.06
χ^2 / sd	$0 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 3$	2,203

Prior to conducting the structural equation modeling (SEM) test, a measurement model was developed and assessed to determine the co-modelability of the elements inside the structural model. Upon examination of the analysis results, it is observed that the calculated value for the measurement model's χ^2 is 572,833, with a corresponding degree of freedom of 260 ($\chi^2 / sd = 2.203$). The expression " χ^2 " refers to the square of the variable " The criteria used in this study was the value of χ^2 / sd , which is less influenced by the sample size. Upon examination of the additional goodness-of-fit indices (RMSEA= 0.060; SRMR= 0.05; NFI=0.92; CFI= 0.95; GFI=0.90; AGFI= 0.88) pertaining to the measurement model, it is evident that the model demonstrates an adequate degree of fit. Consequently, due to the compatibility of the measurement model, the decision was made to use the structural model.

Analysis Results Regarding the Structural Model

Hypotheses tested in the research model

H1: Rational decision making has an impact on real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H 2: Intuitive decision making has an impact on real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H 3: Dependent decision making has an impact on real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H 4: Quick decision making has an impact on real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

H5: Decision avoidance has an impact on real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies.

The stated hypotheses were evaluated based on the values derived from the structural model. The structural model, which incorporates standardized data, is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 3. Model structural model path diagram

Upon examining Figure 9, which displays the path diagram of the structural model, it becomes evident that the item rkv4, with a value of 0.87 on the RKV scale, namely "I need to think carefully to make a decision," emerges as the most influential item. Similarly, the item skv2, with a value of 0.87 on the SKV scale, specifically "I usually tend to rely on my intuition when making decisions," stands out as the most influential item. The item with the highest effectiveness on the BKV scale, measuring 0.78 BKV5, is identified. I find it beneficial to have a knowledgeable somebody who can provide guidance and steer me towards the appropriate course of action when confronted with significant choices. The item with the highest efficacy

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on the KVK platform, with a value of 0.87 in the context of KVK3. When faced with significant judgments, I often exhibit a tendency to defer the handling of item hkv1, which has a notable value of 0.86 on the HKV scale, thus rendering it the most efficacious item. Consequently, I express a need to acquire an installed system that provides visibility into the greatest costs as well as the average prices. The compound was determined to be the most efficacious substance.

Once the essential criteria for goodness of fit indices were satisfied in the measurement model of the examined research, the structural model test was conducted. The fit index values of the structural model are shown in Table 23. Two of the index values often used in academic research are the Normed Fit Index (NFI) and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) are both commonly used measures in the field of statistics to assess the adequacy of a statistical model. The Goodness of Fit index, sometimes referred to as AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index), is a statistical measure used to assess the adequacy of a statistical model in fitting observed data. The GFI value was adjusted by using the sample size and the SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual). The square root of standardized mean errors, often known as the root mean square error approximation (RMSEA), is a statistical measure. The root mean square of estimated errors, denoted as χ^2 / sd , is calculated by dividing the chi square value by the degrees of freedom.

Table 6. Fit index values of the structural model

Index	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	Results
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI \leq 0.95$	0.92
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0.95
GFI	$0.90 \leq GFI \leq 0.95$	$0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	0.91
AGFI	$0.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$0.85 \leq AGFI \leq 0.90$	0.88
SRMR	$0.00 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.04
RMSEA	$0.00 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.05
χ^2 / sd	$0 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / sd \leq 3$	2,223

The structural model's predicted value for the chi-square statistic (χ^2) is 577.915, with 260 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2/df = 2.223$). The criteria used in this study was the value of $\chi^2 /$

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sd, which is less influenced by the sample size. Upon examination of various goodness-of-fit indices (RMSEA= 0.050; SRMR= 0.040; NFI=0.92; CFI= 0.95; GFI=0.91; AGFI=0.88) pertaining to the measurement model, it is evident that the model demonstrates a satisfactory degree of fit.

Table 7. Parameter values of the structural model

Factors/ Substances		Standardized Parameter Estimate Values	t -value	p -value
RKV --- > BEK		0.292	4,669	<0.05
SKV ---> BEK		-0.021	-0.348	>0.05
BKV ---> BEK		0.178	2,972	<0.05
KVK ---> BEK		-0.078	-1.252	>0.05
HKV---> BEK		0.087	1,393	>0.05
RKV	Rkv5	0.818		
	Rkv4	0.866	19,836	<0.05
	Rkv3	0.757	16,977	<0.05
	Rkv2	0.749	16,757	<0.05
SKV	Skv5	0.700		
	Skv2	0.866	14,514	<0.05
	Skv1	0.789	14,192	<0.05
BKV	Bkv5	0.775		
	Bkv4	0.767	13,875	<0.05
	Bkv3	0.753	13,762	<0.05
KVK	Kvk5	0.827		
	Kvk3	0.874	19,454	<0.05
	Kvk2	0.795	17,985	<0.05
HKV	hkv3	0.579		
	hkv2	0.857	12,003	<0.05
	hkv1	0.859	12,003	<0.05
BACK	Bek7	0.845		

	Bek8	0.835	22,050	<0.05
	Full 9	0.842	22,398	<0.05
	full 10	0.854	22,955	<0.05
	fullback11	0.874	23,894	<0.05
	fullback12	0.828	21,746	<0.05
	fullback13	0.805	20,759	<0.05
	fullback17	0.803	20,674	<0.05
	Wait19	0.785	19,968	<0.05

*p<0.05

Table 8. Hypothesis results for the model

Hypothesis No.	hypotheses	Results
H 11	RKV --- > BEK	Accepted.
H 12	SKV ---> BEK	Denied.
H 13	BKV ---> BEK	Accepted.
H 14	KVK ---> BEK	Denied.
H 15	HKV---> BEK	Denied.

Upon examining the results obtained from the analysis of the five predetermined hypotheses, it was found that the H1 hypothesis, which suggests a significant relationship between rational decision-making style and real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies, was accepted at a significance level of 0.05. Furthermore, the hypothesis that the H3 hypothesis has statistical significance, indicating that the dependent decision-making style has a major impact on the expectations of real estate clients about digital technologies, was deemed acceptable at a significance level of 0.05.

Research model reliability analyzes

In order for a scale to be considered appropriate for use in research or assessment, it is essential that it have both validity and reliability. The investigation of validity led to the

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conclusion that the model III scale demonstrates validity. Hence, to assess the scale's reliability, the Cronbach Alpha (CA) test is used. The CA test is utilized for examining the reliability of the scale. The provided information includes the internal consistency coefficient, which is derived from the double correlation. Additionally, it includes the Combined Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. The Cronbach Alpha (CA) values for the scale are provided in Table 10.

Table 9. Evaluation of scale reliability according to alpha value (Özdamar, 2017)

$\alpha < 0.50$	The scale is unreliable
$0.50 \leq \alpha < 0.60$	The scale is low reliable.
$0.60 \leq \alpha < 0.70$	The scale is moderately reliable
$0.70 \leq \alpha < 0.80$	The scale is reliable at a generally accepted level .
$0.80 \leq \alpha < 0.90$	The scale is highly reliable.
$\alpha \geq 0.90$	The scale is perfectly reliable.

Table 10. CA (Cronbach Alpha) values of the Model Scale

Factor	Number of items	CA (Cronbach Alpha)
BACK	9	0.95
KVK	3	0.87
RKV	4	0.87
SKV	3	0.83
BKV	3	0.81
HKV	3	0.81
full scale	25	0.85

Upon examination of Table 10, reliability values are provided for each individual element as well as for the overall scale. Based on the observed reliability values above 0.70, it can be inferred that the scale exhibits a satisfactory level of dependability. In situations when there is a substantial quantity of items, the usage of coefficient omega hierarchical (CR) may serve as a viable substitute for Cronbach Alpha (CA). The term "CR value" is often referred to as composite reliability in academic literature. The CR (Combined Reliability) value must exceed 0.70, similar to the CA (Cronbach Alpha) number. The AVE (Mean Explained Variance) value,

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sometimes referred to as the mean explained variance, is calculated by dividing the factor-related expressions by the sum of the squared covariances. According to Hair (1998), it is anticipated that the Average Explained Variance (AVE) values would exceed 0.50. Table 27 presents the CR (Combined Reliability) and AVE (Mean Explained Variance) values for the factors.

CR (Combined Reliability) and AVE (Mean Explained Variance) values for the factors of the model scale

Sub-Factors	CR (Combined Confidence)	AVE (Average Explained Variance)
BACK	0.96	0.71
KVK	0.90	0.75
RKV	0.89	0.67
SKV	0.87	0.69
BKV	0.87	0.68
HKV	0.86	0.67

The observed data indicates that the scale has a satisfactory level of reliability, as shown by the fact that the Combined Reliability (CR) values exceed 0.70 and the Mean Explained Variance (AVE) values exceed 0.50.

CONCLUSION

The previous model examined the direct impact of decision-making styles on the expectations of real estate customers regarding digital technologies. The hypotheses regarding the direct effects of rational decision-making style and dependent decision-making styles on real estate customers' expectations from digital technologies were found to be statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05.

The influence of rational decision-making on expectations about digital technologies is evident, since consumers rely on these tools to get precise information.

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In contemporary times, there exists a prevailing inclination among real estate consumers to engage in preliminary online investigations before embarking on physical visits to selected homes. One may argue that the practice of completing preliminary research on the internet and narrowing down possibilities may have resulted in a kind of addiction, leading to a heightened reliance on digital technology among real estate clients, hence increasing their expectations.

RESTRICTION

In this study, which is built around a better understanding of the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, the boundaries of these two concepts are determined and this evaluation is carried out with the information provided from the sources obtained by taking into account the scope of the research. This study is globally limited to the scientific studies on the subject.

NOTICES

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external experts.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Financial Support: The author did not report any financial support for the study.

ETHICS DECLARATION

The publication ethics of this journal; It is a scientific journal in the field of social sciences that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with the main criteria specified as openness, honesty, respect for the findings and work of other publishers and objectivity.

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